

**BACTERIOLOGICAL STUDY IN CULTURED PRAWN
(*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*) GHERS OF TWO UPAZILA
UNDER KHULNA DISTRICT**

MS Thesis

SEIKH RAZIBUL ISLAM

Department of Fisheries Technology
Bangladesh Agricultural University
Mymensingh

June, 2014

**BACTERIOLOGICAL STUDY IN CULTURED PRAWN
(*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*) GHERS OF TWO UPAZILA
UNDER KHULNA DISTRICT**

A Thesis

Submitted to
Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh
In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Master of Science
in

Fisheries Technology

By

SEIKH RAZIBUL ISLAM

Roll No. 13 FT JJ- 02M

Registration No.: 40877 Session: 2013-2014

Department of Fisheries Technology
Bangladesh Agricultural University
Mymensingh

June, 2014

**BACTERIOLOGICAL STUDY IN CULTURED PRAWN
(*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*) GHERS OF TWO UPAZILA
UNDER KHULNA DISTRICT**

A Thesis

Submitted to
Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh
In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Master of Science
in

Fisheries Technology

By

SEIKH RAZIBUL ISLAM

Approved as to style and contents by

.....
Prof. Dr. Md. Naim Uddin
Supervisor

.....
Dr. Md. Khalilur Rahman
Co-Supervisor

.....
Dr. Md. Shaheed Reza
Associate Professor
Chairman, Examination Committee
&
Head, Department of Fisheries Technology

June, 2014

Dedicated To
My
Beloved Parents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author expresses his gratitude and praises to the almighty Allah who enabled him to pursue higher studies as well as to submit the thesis for the degree of Master of Science in Fisheries Technology.

The author feels fortunate to get Professor Dr. Md. Naim Uddin, Department of Fisheries Technology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, not only as his supervisor, but as a mentor and would like to express deep respect and gratitude for his scholastic supervision, pretty guidance, affectionate support, and immense help throughout the entire period of planning, conducting, and completing research work and preparation of the thesis.

With equal gratitude, the author would like to express heartfelt respect to his co-supervisor, Dr. Md. Khalilur Rahman, Principal Scientific Officer and Project Director, Bangladesh Fisheries Research Institute, Freshwater Station, Mymensingh, for his kind co-operation for the thesis work. Much of the analysis and theoretical development in this thesis would not have been possible without his patient review, comments, and suggestions.

The author feels great pleasure in expressing his deep sense of respect and gratitude to his teacher, Associate Professor Dr. Md. Shaheed Reza, Head and Chairman of the Examination Committee, Department of Fisheries Technology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, for his inspiration and valuable advice during the research work and preparation of the thesis.

The author wishes to acknowledge his gratitude to Prof. Dr. Md. Nazrul Islam, Prof. Dr. Md. Kamal, Prof. Dr. S.C. Chakraborty, Prof. Dr. Md. Abul Mansur, Prof. Dr. A.K.M. Nowsad Alam, Prof. Dr. Fatema Hoque Shikha and Prof. Dr. Md. Ismail Hossain, Department of Fisheries Technology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, for their help, cordial feelings, brilliant advice, and fruitful suggestions to carry out the research work successfully.

The author desires to acknowledge his heartfelt appreciation and profound thanks to all his friends who helped in the data collection specially Mohsina Mannan and Mahadi Hasan Osman. The author is also grateful to the Upazila Fisheries Officers and different

gher owners at Batiaghata and Rupsha Upazila for providing different types of samples and giving necessary information.

The author also extends thanks to Md. Aoulad Hossain and other laboratory personnel of the Department of Fisheries Technology for their active co-operation, overall assistance and friendly behavior during the experimental period.

Finally, the author expresses his deepest respect to his beloved parents Mr. Seikh Hemayet Uddin and Mrs. Aleya Begum for their sacrifices, inspirations, moral support, kindness and blessings, forbearance, and endless love not only during the study period but also for the entire period of life.

The Author

BACTERIOLOGICAL STUDY IN CULTURED PRAWN (*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*) GHERS OF TWO UPAZILA UNDER KHULNA DISTRICT

SEIKH RAZIBUL ISLAM

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted for bacteriological analysis and to determine the physico-chemical parameters of two prawn ghers from Batiaghata and Rupsha upazila under Khulna district. The ghers were designated as gher 1 and gher 2, respectively. Duration of the study was from December, 2013 to May, 2014. The study included physico-chemical parameters like water temperature, dissolve oxygen (DO), pH and salinity of gher water; bacteriological study like aerobic plate count and presence of enteric bacteria in gher water, sediment and prawn samples. Total three samplings were done with one month interval. The samples were collected from three different corner of the gher. Mean water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), dissolve oxygen (mg/l), pH and salinity were 25.73 ± 3.30 , 27.30 ± 3.40 ; 4.90 ± 0.26 , 4.92 ± 0.26 ; 7.13 ± 0.47 , 6.63 ± 0.50 and 7.67 ± 1.53 , 9.33 ± 1.15 in gher 1 and 2, respectively. In gher 1, total viable count of bacteria in water, ranged 2.56×10^4 to 8.65×10^4 and 1.54×10^5 to 8.31×10^5 ; in sediment, ranged from 6.01×10^8 to 1.51×10^9 and 4.55×10^9 to 9.52×10^9 ; in prawn, ranged from 2.95×10^6 to 2.33×10^7 and 4.30×10^7 to 1.18×10^8 in gher analysis and laboratory analysis, respectively. In gher 2, it ranged from 6.52×10^4 to 1.30×10^5 and 7.30×10^5 to 1.89×10^6 in water; 9.63×10^8 to 1.12×10^9 and 9.29×10^9 to 3.18×10^{10} in sediment; 2.50×10^6 to 9.16×10^6 and 4.25×10^7 to 3.08×10^8 in prawn in gher analysis and laboratory analysis, respectively. The differences between gher and laboratory analysis were occurred due to the change of freshness and time interval. The differences between the two ghers might be the different geographical location, different management practices etc. Temperature may be the major factor in decreasing or increasing bacterial loads in the gher water, sediment and prawn samples. Enteric bacteria were present in both the ghers. The presence of enteric bacteria in the gher water, sediment and prawn samples suggested that water was polluted with feed and bird faeces. The present study on the bacteriology of two prawn ghers was very useful in gathering a lot of valuable information regarding the physico-chemical parameters of gher water and the bacterial load of gher water, sediment and prawn samples. The apparent difference in the bacteriological condition of the two ghers makes it justifiable to assume that bacteriological condition has some direct or indirect relationship with the productivity of the ghers.

CONTENTS

CHAPTER	TITLE	PAGE
	ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	v
	ABSTRACT	vii
	CONTENTS	viii
	LIST OF TABLES	ix
	LIST OF FIGURES	x
	LIST OF PLATES	xi
1	INTRODUCTION	01
2	REVIEW OF LITERATURE	07
3	MATERIALS AND METHODS	12
4	RESULTS	28
5	DISCUSSION	42
6	SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION	46
	REFERENCES	48

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE	TITLE	PAGE
1	Physicochemical parameters of gher 1	28
2	Bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn of gher 1 (fresh samples)	29
3	Bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn of gher 1 (iced samples)	29
4	Number of enteric bacteria in water sample of gher 1	30
5	Number of enteric bacteria in sediment sample of gher 1	31
6	Number of enteric bacteria in prawn sample of gher 1	32
7	Total number of bacterial isolates in water, sediment and prawn and percentage of Gram +ve and Gram –ve bacteria	33
8	Physicochemical parameters of gher 2	34
9	Bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn of gher 2 (fresh samples)	35
10	Bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn of gher 2 (iced samples)	35
11	Number of enteric bacteria in water sample of gher 2	36
12	Number of enteric bacteria in sediment sample of gher 2	37
13	Number of enteric bacteria in prawn sample of gher 2	38
14	Total number of bacterial isolates in gher 2 water, sediment and prawn and percentage of Gram +ve and Gram –ve bacteria	39
15	Comparative study of bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn, between gher 1 and gher 2.	40

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE	TITLE	PAGE
1	Design of the research methodology	12
2	Location of gher 1 in Batiaghata upazila	13
3	Location of gher 2 in Rupsha upazila	14
4	Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of water sample	30
5	Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of sediment sample	31
6	Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of prawn sample	32
7	Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of water sample	36
8	Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of sediment sample	37
9	Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of prawn sample	38
10	Comparative study of bacterial load between gher 1 and gher 2	41

LIST OF PLATES

PLATE	TITLE	PAGE
1	pH and salinity measurement at gher	15
2	Collection of water and sediment samples	16
3	Marking of the collected sample bottle	17
4	Collection of prawn sample	17
5	Preparation of agar plate for bacterial culture	20
6	Culture of bacteria at gher	21
7	Prawn taken for sample preparation in laboratory	23
8	Prepared sample of prawn (whole body of three individual)	23
9	Culture of bacteria in laboratory	24
10	Bacterial colony in agar plate and colony count	25
11	Growth of enteric bacteria in selective media	26

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture is one of the fastest-growing food producing sectors throughout the world. Now aquaculture plays a vital role to fulfill our domestic demand of protein and also we earn a lot of foreign exchange by exporting fishes and fisheries product. Fish alone supplies about 60 percent of animal protein and about 10.5 million people are directly or indirectly earn their livelihood out of activity related to fisheries (DoF, 2012). Fisheries resources have great contribution in the economy of Bangladesh accounting for about 4.39% of GDP. About 2.46% of annual export earning comes from the fisheries sector and it ranks 3rd among the export oriented industries (DoF, 2013). Prawn sector plays a major role in public health sector in Bangladesh. It contributes a lot in the national economy generating employment and foreign exchange earnings. About two million people are associated with prawn sector for employment and foreign exchange earnings (Azim *et al.*, 2002). In 2008-2009 Bangladesh earned TK. 27,441.2 million by exporting 50,368 tons prawn (DoF, 2008).

The culture of giant freshwater prawn is being practiced on commercial scale in several parts of the world especially in South East Asia. Bangladesh with its favorable resources and agro-climatic conditions is widely recognized as one of the most suitable countries in the world for giant freshwater prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* (De Man, 1879) farming.

The success of practical aquaculture depends on water quality which is greatly influenced by aquatic microorganisms. Aquatic microorganisms influence the water and sediment quality and are closely associated with the fish physiology, diseases and aquaculture. Fish take a large number of bacteria into their gut from water, sediment and food (Sugita *et al.*, 1985). Shewan and Hobbs (1967) suggested that the bacterial flora on fish reflects the aquatic environment. Bacteria in sediments are major contributors to bio-geochemical processes in benthic ecosystems and bacterial abundance is an important parameter for

assessing the roles of bacteria in these environments (Liao *et al.*, 2012). The sediment is a more appropriate medium to sample than the water column because it is less influenced by perturbations caused by rainfall and transient movements of waterborne substances (Al-Harbi and Uddin, 2006). Fish farming activity has a comparatively lower impact on the water environment than on the sediment (La Rosa *et al.*, 2004).

Some common bacterial microflora in water such as *Pseudomonas*, *Aeromonas* and *Vibrio* can cause major fish epizootics under stressful conditions. The bacterial content of the sediments affects the quality of fish and fish products. Evidence indicates that the gastrointestinal microflora of fish is highly variable and is a reflection of their aqueous environment especially the food and sediments (Campbell and Buswell, 1983; Nieto *et al.*, 1984).

Despite of this, very little attention has been paid to the bacterial flora associated with cultured *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* (Miyamoto *et al.*, 1983) and its influence on the initial quality of this prawn species. For the favorable soil and climatic condition the area of the freshwater prawn culture is expanding every year. The pace of adoption increased dramatically, and this technology spread to other southwest districts such as Khulna and Satkhira. Since 2000, the increased demand for prawn in the international market has attracted many fish farmers to prawn cultivation in freshwater and low-saline waters in different parts of Bangladesh, mainly Noakhali, Patuakhali, Mymensingh, Khulna and Bagerhat districts (Asaduzzaman *et al.*, 2007).

In Khulna region Batiaghata and Rupsha are the potential places for prawn culture due to the availability of freshwater or low saline water. In Bangladesh, most of the farmers use organic manures like cow dung and poultry faeces in addition to chemical fertilizers. It creates the chance of integration of *Salmonella*, *Cholera* and other pathogenic bacteria in the ponds. In the foreign markets, fresh water prawns of Bangladesh have been rejected mainly due to the contamination of *Salmonella*, and faecal coliforms and rarely for *Vibrio cholerae*, but in the major cases for *Salmonella*. The rejection of prawn consignment both

internally and in the foreign market is involved with huge amount of financial loss to the nation which ultimately severely affects the prawn farmer and all other stakeholders. Types and levels of bacterial populations associated with farmed giant fresh water prawn (*M. rosenbergii*), water and sediments are the important indicators for the assessment of quality and safety of prawns. In addition, most diseases in *M. rosenbergii* are caused by opportunistic pathogens which are prevalent in the rearing environment (Janaki and Madhavi, 1999). Therefore, it is essential to investigate the quantitative and qualitative aspects of bacterial flora associated with cultured fresh water prawn and particularly those of public health concern in order to develop a “Good Aquaculture Practice” (GAP) for the production of prawn safe for human consumption and for prevention of prawn diseases. Prevention or control of fish disease is essential to the success of the large-scale, production of fish. Generally, the prawn farmers do not know about the bacterial status of farmed prawn and also do not know the sources of bacterial contamination in their culture ponds. Therefore, to enrich the knowledge of the fresh water prawn farmers and to develop a good management practice for the production of prawn safe for human consumption and for the prevention of diseases, it is important to study the bacterial contents of prawn, water and sediment of the pond during culture.

Pond bottom soils are an integral part of the pond ecosystem (Boyd, 1995; Boyd and Bowman, 1997). They can act as a biological filter, adsorbing organic residues of food, fish excretions and algal metabolites (Avnimelech and Lacher, 1980). Perhaps more importantly, pond sediments play a significant role in the cycling of nutrients in a fertilized pond (Avnimelech and Lacher, 1979; Boyd, 1995). Microorganisms particularly bacteria plays a vital role in the pond ecosystem. They plays both beneficial (nutrients recycling, organic matter degrading etc.) and harmful roles as parasites in the pond ecosystem (Rheinheimer, 1985). Apart from indigenous bacteria in estuarine water, application of artificial feed and fertilizers, high stocking density, induced breeding and shallow nature of water in intensive and semi intensive farm

leads to high bacterial population and thus cause diseases in pond reared animals.

Nutrient losses to sediments occur with the sedimentation of P, N, and C bound up in particulate organic matter, particularly algal-based detritus. Sedimentation rates are higher in fertilized systems (Hepher, 1965). Other losses to the sediments include the rapid chemical adsorption of P and ammonia to inorganic sediments. In fact, sediment conditions created in highly productive ponds facilitate nutrient transport from the pond bottom. Sediments in fertilized culture ponds typically become void of dissolved oxygen due to the accumulation of decomposing organic matter. Under anaerobic conditions, the chemical solubility's of dissolved P, ammonia, and CO₂ increase in the interstitial water (i.e., water between sediment granules). Bottom water, overlying pond sediments, can have elevated concentrations of these algal nutrients that accumulate during day-time thermal stratification. Nighttime mixing brings this nutrient-rich bottom water upward, and at the same time transports oxygen-rich surface water down to the sediments (Nealson, 1997).

The prokaryotes (bacteria) comprise the bulk of the biomass and chemical activity in sediments. They are well suited to their role as sediment chemists, as they are the right size and have the required metabolic versatility to oxidize the organic carbon in a variety of different ways. The characteristic vertical nutrient (electron donor and electron acceptor) profiles seen in sediments are produced as a result of microbial activities, with each nutrient a product or reactant of one or more metabolic groups. Thus, understanding the mechanisms by which the chemical environment of sediment is generated and stabilized requires knowledge of resident populations (Nealson, 1997).

The bacteriology of pond sediments is largely driven by type of diet added to ponds, ambient temperature and limiting levels of oxygen (Smith, 1993). Bacteria are responsible for many of the dominant chemical processes that occur in earthen fish ponds and they are either the primary or secondary pathogens in many infectious diseases (Lightner, 1996). Microorganisms help not only in the

production and breakdown of organic matter, but also in the nutrient recycling in the aquatic ecosystem. Of the different pond habitats, sediments harbor the greatest number of aquatic microorganisms. Water quality and disease control are interdependent and linked to the microbial activities in aquaculture systems. Microbial processes affect water quality factors (Moriarty, 1997).

Bacteria present in the aquatic environment, such as *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Edwardsiella tarda* and *Vibrio* spp. can cause major fish epizootics under stressful conditions (Ninagawa *et al.*, 1983 and Sugita *et al.*, 1985). The level of *Vibrio* spp. in pond sediment is an important parameter to monitor because it is an indicator of bacterial load and stress on the fish (Smith, 1993 and La rosa *et al.*, 2002). Management of pond sediments may be a key factor influencing the bacteriology of earthen fish ponds and health of fish during grow-out. Conditions leading to development of fish diseases may be recognized and corrected. Detailed information about microbial load and types of bacteria in pond sediments is essential. The above discussion should be sufficient enough to justify the necessity of undertaking this research programme.

Knowledge about bacterial community structure and diversity is essential to understand the relationship between environmental factors and ecosystem functions. Such Knowledge can be used to assess the effect on ecosystem of environmental stress and perturbations like pollution, agricultural exploitation and global changes. Therefore studying aquatic microbiology is a crying need for water quality management both in aquaculture and public health. Detailed information about the microbial load and types of bacteria in fish culture pond water is essential in order to recognize and correct the abnormal conditions of fish which can be a prelude to the appearance of disease epizootics.

Objectives of the study

Considering the enormous importance, the present study has been undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To determine physico-chemical parameters of prawn ghers such as temperature, pH, salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO);
2. To determine total bacterial load of water, sediment and prawn in two prawn ghers; and
3. To determine the presence of enteric bacteria in water, sediment and prawn samples.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The present research was on bacteriology of prawn ghers with special emphasis on prawn. The available literatures on prawn ghers in Khulna region of Bangladesh are very few. Available literatures related to the present study were reviewed and summarized below:

2.1 Physico-chemical parameters

The term water quality in its broadest sense includes all physical, chemical and biological characteristics of water (Boyd, 1995). Physical, chemical and biological aspects of water influence the ability of aquatic organisms to perform physiological functions, including growth, disease resistance, reproduction, and tolerance to extreme temperature.

Dissolved oxygen concentration is one of the vital water quality parameter in aquaculture. Maintenance of sufficient dissolved oxygen in ponds at all time is, undoubtedly, the most essential task of water quality management performed by fish culturists. The sudden drop of dissolved oxygen causes heavy mortality. Kunda *et al.* (2008) found DO values ranged from 5.98 to 6.53 mg/l.

pH of water is a good indicator of pond productivity (Boyd, 1992). It determines the nutrients remain in dissolved state. pH is considered as an important factor in prawn culture and is treated as the index of several environmental conditions, such as free carbon dioxide concentration, dissolved oxygen concentration, concentration of nutrients, acidity-alkalinity etc. A high pH value can cause fish mortality through direct pH toxicity, and indirectly through higher percentage of total ammonia in the water as toxic unionized form. The pH value ranged from 7.5 to 8.0 was suitable for fish culture in earthen ponds (Jia-Mao *et al.*, 1988).

2.2 Bacteriology of prawn ghers

A thorough search of literature on the bacteriology of pond soil revealed that very few information are available on the bacteriology of pond bottom soil of Bangladesh. But numerous reports are available on the bacteriology of pond soil from different parts of the world. The literature reviewed here will include those relevant to the present study.

Bacterial diversity has become an important issue due to the importance of bacteria in energy and matter transportation. Knowledge about bacterial community structure and diversity is essential to understand the relationship between environmental factors and ecosystem functions. Such Knowledge can be used to assess the effect on ecosystem of environmental stress and perturbations like pollution, agricultural exploitation and global changes. It is also realized that the functional and genetic potential of the microorganisms may exceed that of higher organism and provide a valuable source for novel products and technologies. Despite their importance, at the present the magnitude of the bacterial diversity in most ecosystems is not even known. The measure of bacterial diversity describes the qualitative variation among these organisms in a community or assemblage. Diversity can also be regarded as the amount of information or species richness in a community (Torsvik *et al.*, 1996).

Van Duyl *et al.* (1993) examined the relationship between benthic bacterial production and biomass and sediment-water exchange rates of inorganic nutrients in the North Sea in summer. The sediments were sandy, poor in organic matter and with low buffering capacities for nutrients and significant negative relations between bacterial production and sediment-water fluxes of nutrients was observed.

Burford *et al.* (1998) examined sediment bacteria in intensive shrimp (*Penaeus monodon*) ponds in tropical Australia. At the end of the production season it was found that the pond centre, containing flocculated sludge, had significantly higher bacterial counts (15.5×10^9 /g dw) than the pond periphery (8.1×10^9 /g dw). It was also found that Bacterial numbers were highly correlated with

organic carbon and total kjeldahl nitrogen in the sediment, suggesting that these were limiting factors to bacterial growth.

Al- Harbi (2003) undertook a study on total bacterial load, total coliforms and faecal coliforms in pond water, sediment, and intestine of hybrid tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Oreochromis aureus* and pigeon *Columba livia* faeces over a period of one year in Saudi Arabia. Results showed total viable bacterial counts in the sediment was $3.2 \pm 1.2 \times 10^5$ to $2.8 \pm 1.5 \times 10^7$ cfu/g and the abundance of normal bacteria and coliforms were greater in the warm months than in the cold months.

Al-Harbi and Uddin (2003) estimated bacterial flora of the rearing pond water and sediment quantitatively and qualitatively. Total viable count of bacteria in sediment was $93 \pm 1.1 \times 10^6$ to $1.9 \pm 1.5 \times 10^8$ cfu/g.

Ogbulie and Cobiajuru (2003) carried out a study on the impact of seasonal changes on the bacteriological water quality in a *Clarius lazera* culture system in Nigeria. Stratification was observed in the bacterial distribution with the pond sediment favoring more aerobic and anaerobic bacterial genera than the pond water.

Logue *et al.* (2004) investigated sediment bacteria whether related to sediment organic content in 11 nonforested streams of three different Alpine catchments in America during summer and also tested seasonal and spatial differences in bacterial composition in these same streams. Results showed that the percentage of organic matter of sediments was 4-14% and counts of bacteria cells per millimeter of sediment averaged 4×10^6 cfu/g. It was also found that bacterial composition changed seasonally in the different streams and differed between glacial- fed and groundwater- fed streams.

Al-Harbi and Uddin (2005) estimated bacterial flora occurring in brackish pond water, sediment, gills and intestine of healthy tilapia cultured in Saudi Arabia both quantitatively and qualitatively, and the isolates were identified to genus or species level. Total viable count of bacteria ranged from $1.2 \pm 3.1 \times 10^6$ to

$7.3 \pm 1.1 \times 10^7$ cfu/g in the pond sediment. In total, 19 bacterial species were identified. The bacteria were predominantly gram-negative rods (87%).

Sestanovic *et al.* (2005) worked on volume, abundance and biomass of sediment bacteria in the eastern mid Adriatic Sea for one year. The number of bacteria varied from 3.54×10^9 cfu/g in July to 8.08×10^9 cfu/g in September.

Al-Harbi and Uddin (2006) carried out a study on the bacterial flora in pond sediments in Saudi Arabia. Bacterial numbers (cfu/g) seemed to be highest in summer. Results showed that total viable counts (TVC) of bacteria in the pond sediments varied between $5.2 \pm 2.7 \times 10^7$ to $1.4 \pm 2.3 \times 10^8$ cfu/g in early summer, $6.6 \pm 2.4 \times 10^8$ to $8.9 \pm 2.0 \times 10^9$ cfu/g, significantly higher ($P < 0.005$) in summer, $4.2 \pm 2.8 \times 10^7$ to $6.3 \pm 1.7 \times 10^6$ cfu/g, significantly lower ($P < 0.005$) in autumn, and $7.9 \pm 1.9 \times 10^5$ to $8.6 \pm 2.1 \times 10^6$ cfu/g in winter. A total of 20 bacterial species were identified from the sediment. It was also found that the bacteria were predominantly gram negative rods (77%). *Aeromonas hydrophila* was 27%, significantly higher ($P < 0.005$) in the population.

Fierer and Jackson (2006) found that bacterial diversity was unrelated to site temperature, latitude, and other variables that typically predict plant and animal diversity and community composition was largely independent of geographic distance. It was suggested that the diversity and richness of soil bacterial communities differed by ecosystem type and these differences could largely be explained by soil pH and bacterial diversity was highest in neutral soils and lower in acidic soils.

Zhang *et al.* (2009) worked on bacterial community structure and the relationship between environmental variables and microbial communities in the surface sediments of tropical mangrove ecosystems in China. Findings suggested that microbial communities varied with sample collections sites and seasons.

Walling *et al.* (2010) observed *Vibrio nigripulchritudo* and strain dynamics in shrimp pond sediments. The study confirmed the presence of pathogenic *V. nigripulchritudo* strains in shrimp pond sediment before a mortality outbreak

complying with a previous hypothesis that sediments could be the infecting reservoir. It was observed that after the outbreak, both total *V. nigripulchritudo* and pathogenic strains populations have largely increased, possibly contributing to the recurrent mortality observed in this shrimp vibriosis.

Zeng *et al.* (2010) conducted a study on bacterial diversity in various coastal mariculture ponds in Southeast China. It was found that pond sediment showed a much more complex bacterial community than surface water.

Shao *et al.* (2011) investigated bacterial community structure and effects of several environmental factors on bacteria community distribution in the sediment of the macrophyte- dominated and algae- dominated areas in a large, shallow, eutrophic freshwater lake (Lake Taihu, China). Results showed that there were significant seasonal variations in the structure of the sediment bacterial community in the macrophyte-dominated and algae-dominated areas, and site-specific variation within an area and between 2 areas, and there were no significant difference between- area variations due to the large within- area variation. Results also showed that total phosphorus and water temperature were the dominant environmental factors affecting bacterial community composition in the sediment.

CHAPTER 3

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This chapter describes the research methodology followed to achieve the objectives of the study and explains the choice for selecting research tools and methods for data collection. It also portrays the research area, sample collection, laboratory analysis, and selection of analytical methods that have been used in the study.

The study had been undertaken and completed according to the following order of methodology (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Design of the research methodology

3.1 Duration of the study

The present study was conducted during the months of December, 2013 to May, 2014.

3.2 Description of the ghers

The present study was carried out in two ghers located at Batiaghata and Rupsha upazila under Khulna district. Both the ghers were supplied with ground water as a major source. Intrusion of saline water was also observed. Gher 2 was comparatively larger (7 acres) than gher 1 (3.5 acres). Both the ghers were surrounded by paddy fields. Higher levels of mud on the bottom were observed (8 cm in gher 1 and 12 cm in gher 2). Use of feed in both prawn gher was common.

Figure 2. Location of gher 1 in Batiaghata upazila

Figure 3. Location of gher 2 in Rupsha upazila

3.3 Procedure of study

3.3.1 Sources of samples

For bacteriological analysis water, sediment and prawn samples were collected from two gher located at Batiaghata and Rupsha upazila under Khulna district. Those two gher were designated as gher 1 and gher 2, respectively. The samplings were done three time with one month interval. In each sampling two parallel samples of water, sediment and prawn were collected from each gher. In each gher three locations were selected for sample collection and collected samples were mixed together to make a representative sample and were kept in two separate sterilized plastic bottles (to analyze one at the gher and one in laboratory).

3.3.2 Recording of physico-chemical parameters

During collection of samples surface water temperature and air temperature was measured by a simple thermometer. pH of water and sediment were measured by pH paper stripes. Salinity and dissolved oxygen (DO) were also measured by using laboratory kit and reagents (Plate 1).

Plate 1. pH (a) and salinity (b) measurement at gher

3.3.3 Collection and transportation of samples

During sampling, a total of 6 samples were taken from each gher; two water samples, two sediment samples and two prawn samples. Each water sample was collected by submerging clean, sterilized plastic bottles (250 ml) 15-20 cm below the water surface at three different locations in each gher with slight water level variation and mixed together (Plate 2). Each sediment sample was collected by submerging sterile wide mouth glass bottles (250 ml) from the same (previously stated in case of water sample) three different locations in each gher and also mixed together (Plate 2). Prawn sample was also collected from two to three locations of the gher randomly (15-20 g) (Plate 4). Each collected sample was marked properly with a permanent marker pen and wrapped with aluminium foil and transported to the rest room in the gher (Plate 3). One set of samples was subjected to immediate analysis and rests were kept in ice box with sufficient flake ice to bring to the laboratory within 12-14 hours (as soon as possible). Three samplings were done with monthly interval.

Plate 2. Collection of water (a) and sediment (b) samples

Plate 3. Marking the collected sample bottle

Plate 4. Collection of prawn sample (a, b, c and d)

3.3.4 Preparation of media

The following general procedure was adopted in preparing different media (Plate 5).

3.3.4.1 Mixing the ingredients

The recommended quantities of ingredients were weighed and then dissolved in the required amount of water. The mixture was then boiled on electric heater to mix all the ingredients thoroughly.

3.3.4.2 Sterilization

Media were sterilized before using them in order to kill any bacterial and fungal cells or spores present in the media or in the glass wares containing them. Sterilization was accomplished by placing the media in an autoclave for 20 minutes at a temperature of 121°C under 15 lbs/sq. inch pressure. Then it was cooled down to around 50°C and was poured into previously sterilized petridish.

3.3.4.3 Media used

The following media were used during the work:

a. Agar media

For bacteriological analysis, agar media were prepared by the following composition and procedure:

Plate count agar/ nutrient agar

It was used for total viable count. Plate count agar is a commercial preparation (Hi Media) having the following composition:

Bacto- pepton (Difco)	:	5.0 g
Bacto- meat (beef) extract	:	3.0 g
Bacto-agar	:	15.0 g
Sodium chloride (NaCl)	:	2.0 g
Distilled water	:	1000 ml
Final pH	:	7.2-7.4

For preparation of media, 23.5 g of plate count agar media was weighed and suspended into one litre of distilled water in a conical flask. 2.5% salt (NaCl) was added as the sources of samples were in brackish water body area. Then the mixture was boiled on electric heater to dissolve completely and sterilized.

b. Selective media

Eosin methylene blue (EMB) agar and *Salmonella-Shigella* (SS) agar were used to detect the presence of enteric bacteria.

Plate 5. Preparation of agar plate for bacterial culture (a, b, c ...)

3.3.5 Bacteriological analysis of fresh sample in gher

After collection of samples from the gher one set of samples were subjected to immediate analysis (bacterial culture in agar plate) which was done in the gher (Plate 6). Though the facility in the gher was so poor, but sufficient precautions were taken. There was no or minimum air flow in the room, two spirit lamp were set. All needed materials like previously prepared agar plate, sterilized physiological saline, sterilized cutting and grinding equipment, sterilized test tubes, sterilized tips, micropipettes etc. were taken to the gher.

Plate 6. Culture of bacteria at gher (a, b, c ...)

3.3.5.1 Dilution and culture for bacteria

Water

Gher water samples were collected in sterile glass bottles (250 ml), 15-20 cm below the water surface from three different locations in each gher at every sampling. Three samples were combined to make a composite sample for bacteriological analysis and were kept in two separate sterilized plastic bottles (to analyze one at the gher and one in laboratory). Appropriate sample dilutions were made (10^{-1} to 10^{-5}) with sterile physiological saline (0.85% w/v NaCl). Aliquots of 0.1 ml of the serial dilutions were pipetted out and transferred aseptically to the agar plates by raising the upper lids sufficient enough to admit the tip of the pipette. The samples pipetted were spread by L-shaped glass rods throughout the surface of the media until the samples were dried out. The plates were then wrapped by aluminium foil and kept in the hotel room, where the temperature was around 30°C; and then were brought to the microbiological laboratory of the Dept. of Fisheries Technology, Faculty of Fisheries, BAU, Mymensingh and put in incubator. After 48 hours of incubation colonies developed were counted. Only the plates having 30 to 300 colonies were counted. Two samples (in each set of samples) were analyzed.

Sediment

Bottom sediment samples were collected, with sterile glass bottles submerged to the bottom, from the same three locations in each gher. Five gram of wet sediment was weighed and dissolved in 200 ml physiological saline to make stock solution. One milliliter of the homogenate was serially diluted (10^{-1} to 10^{-9}) and treated in the same way as the water samples. Two samples were analyzed.

Prawn

Three prawn individual were ground and homogenized for each sample preparation (Plate 7 and Plate 8). Approximately 5 g of each homogenate was then put in a bottle containing 200 ml of sterile saline solution. One milliliter of

each homogenate solution was serially diluted (10^{-1} to 10^{-8}) and treated in the same way as the water samples.

3.3.6 Bacteriological analysis of samples in laboratory

One set of samples were subjected to immediate analysis and another set were kept in ice box with sufficient flake ice to bring to the laboratory Dept. of Fisheries Technology, Faculty of Fisheries, BAU, Mymensingh within 12-14 hours. The samples were analyzed as soon as possible to reduce the bacterial load.

3.3.6.1 Sample preparation and culture

Standard plate count expressed as colony forming units per gram (cfu/g) were determined by using consecutive decimal dilution technique using spread plate method (Plate 9). Stock solutions were prepared for sediment and prawn samples. Water samples were directly diluted. Five gram of sediment and five gram of prawn samples were taken (prawn samples were prepared from whole body of three prawns). The samples were mixed in 200 ml sterile physiological saline separately. Then shaking was done properly. One milliliter sample (water, sediment and prawn's stock solution) was transferred with a micropipette to test tube containing 9 ml of physiological saline. The test tube was shaken thoroughly on a vortex mixture in order to get 10^{-1} dilution of original sample solution. Using the similar process several dilutions of 10^{-2} - 10^{-5} , 10^{-2} - 10^{-9} and 10^{-2} - 10^{-8} were made for water, sediment and prawn, respectively.

Plate 7. Prawn taken for sample preparation in laboratory

Plate 8. Prepared sample of prawn (whole body of three individual)

Plate 9. Culture of bacteria in laboratory (a, b, c and d)

3.3.6.2 Aerobic plate count (APC)

All plates in duplicate on sterile petridish were done on sterile nutrient agar media. From sample solution of different dilutions 0.1 ml samples were taken by a micropipette and transferred aseptically into the pre-prepared agar plates by raising the upper lid sufficient enough to enter the tips of the pipette. The samples were then spread homogenously and carefully by sterile flamed L-shaped glass rod throughout the surface of the media until the sample were dried out. For total heterotrophic aerobic bacterial counts of water, sediment and prawn, all the inoculated plates were incubated at 30°C for 24-48 hours. The colonies units (cfu) were counted under a Quebec dark field colony counter (Leica, Buffalo. NY. USA) equipped with a guide plate ruled in square centimeters. Plates containing 30-300 colonies were used to calculate bacterial load results, recorded as cfu per unit of sample by using following formula:

For water sample:

$$\text{cfu/ml} = \text{No. of colonies on petridish} \times 10 \times \text{dilution factor}$$

For sediment sample:

$$\text{cfu/g} = \frac{\text{No. of colonies on petridish} \times 10 \times \text{dilution factor} \times \text{volume of total stock solution}}{\text{Wt. of sediment (g)}}$$

For prawn sample:

$$\text{cfu/g} = \frac{\text{No. of colonies on petridish} \times 10 \times \text{dilution factor} \times \text{volume of total stock solution}}{\text{Wt. of prawn sample (g)}}$$

Plate 10. Bacterial colony in agar plate (a, b) and colony count (c)

3.3.7 Determination of enteric bacteria by using selective media

Presence of enteric bacteria was determined by using selective media EMB- agar and SS- agar. From each stock solution of water, sediment and prawn, 0.1 ml samples were transferred into the selective media. Growth of bacterial colony in EMB-agar and SS-agar media indicate the presence of enteric bacteria.

Plate 11. Growth of enteric bacteria in selective media (a, b)

3.3.8 Isolation of bacteria

Bacterial colonies were isolated from the water, sediment and prawn of each gher at each sampling. For percent composition, the bacterial colonies were divided into different types according to the colony characteristics of shape, size, elevation, structure, surface, edge, color and opacity, and the number of colonies of each recognizable type was counted. Three to five representatives of each colony type were then streaked on agar plates repeatedly until pure cultures were obtained. The streaked agar plates were incubated at 30°C for two days. Discrete colonies from the streaked agar plates were transferred to agar slants.

3.3.8.1 Gram's staining

A small portion of bacterial culture from freshly prepared agar slants was taken on a grease free clear glass slide with a sterile inoculating loop and prepared smear on the slide. The smear was then dried in air and fixed by passing the

slide 3 to 4 times over a spirit lamp flame. Then it was allowed to cool and flooded with crystal violet solution for approximately 1 minute. Then it was washed with tap water and treated with Gram's iodine solution. After 1 minute the iodine solution was tipped off from the slide by tap water. Then the decolorizing agent, 30% acetone and 70% ethanol mixture was applied to the slide and left for 8-10 seconds and was thoroughly washed with water. Then the smear was flooded with counter stain, safranin for about 1 minute and washed with water. The smear was air dried and microscopically examined under the oil immersion objectives.

3.3.9 Maintenance of stock culture

During the experiment it was necessary to preserve the selected isolates for short term periods. For this purpose, after two days of incubation cultures on agar slants were kept at 4°C for stock and these were transferred to new slants at every 6 weeks intervals.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS

4.1 Bacteriological study of gher 1

4.1.1 Physico-chemical parameters

The water quality parameters were recorded three time with one month interval. Water temperature (°C), pH, and dissolved oxygen (mg/l) were recorded. Water temperature in gher 1 was 22.5 to 29.1°C. The air temperature was recorded as 24.9 to 32.7°C. The pH of water was 6.6 to 7.3. The pH of sediment was recorded 3.5 to 3.9. The salinity of water was 6 to 9 ppt. The dissolved oxygen (DO) of water was 4.70 to 5.20 mg/l (Table 1).

Table 1. Physico-chemical parameters of gher 1

Temperature (°C)		pH		Salinity (ppt.)	DO (mg/l)
Water	Air	Water	Sediment		
25.73±3.30	28.60±3.92	7.13±0.47	3.70±0.20	7.67±1.53	4.90±0.26

*Values given are mean (±SD)

4.1.2 Quantitative analysis of bacteria in gher 1

During the period of study, bacterial loads in gher were 2.56×10^4 - 8.65×10^4 cfu/ml in water; 6.01×10^8 - 1.51×10^9 cfu/g in sediment; 2.95×10^6 - 2.33×10^7 cfu/g in prawn when analysis was done by using fresh samples at gher (Table 2). By using iced samples in laboratory bacterial loads were 1.54×10^5 - 8.31×10^5 cfu/ml in water; 4.55×10^9 - 9.52×10^9 cfu/g in sediment; 4.30×10^7 - 1.18×10^8 cfu/g in prawn during the period of study (Table 3).

Table 2. Bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn of gher 1 (fresh samples)

Category	Sample	Bacterial Load			Mean (\pm SD)
		1 st Sampling	2 nd sampling	3 rd sampling	
Water	Sample 1	4.60×10^4	3.96×10^4	9.89×10^4	
	Sample 2	5.12×10^3	2.54×10^4	7.4×10^4	
	Average	2.56×10^4	3.25×10^4	8.65×10^4	$4.82 \pm 3.33 \times 10^4$
Sediment	Sample 1	9.91×10^7	5.32×10^8	2.74×10^9	
	Sample 2	1.30×10^9	6.70×10^8	2.80×10^8	
	Average	7.00×10^8	6.01×10^8	1.51×10^9	$9.37 \pm 4.99 \times 10^8$
Prawn	Sample 1	4.63×10^6	4.55×10^6	7.36×10^6	
	Sample 2	5.45×10^6	1.35×10^6	3.92×10^7	
	Average	5.04×10^6	2.95×10^6	2.33×10^7	$1.04 \pm 1.12 \times 10^7$

Table 3. Bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn of gher 1 (iced samples)

Category	Sample	Bacterial Load			Mean (\pm SD)
		1 st Sampling	2 nd sampling	3 rd sampling	
Water	Sample 1	1.73×10^5	8.84×10^4	9.45×10^5	
	Sample 2	1.05×10^4	2.20×10^5	7.17×10^5	
	Average	5.78×10^5	1.54×10^5	8.31×10^5	$5.21 \pm 3.42 \times 10^5$
Sediment	Sample 1	8.42×10^8	8.80×10^9	3.05×10^9	
	Sample 2	1.82×10^{10}	8.42×10^8	6.05×10^9	
	Average	9.52×10^9	4.82×10^9	4.55×10^9	$6.30 \pm 2.79 \times 10^9$
Prawn	Sample 1	9.79×10^7	1.49×10^8	2.88×10^7	
	Sample 2	7.63×10^7	8.61×10^7	5.72×10^7	
	Average	8.71×10^7	1.18×10^8	4.30×10^7	$8.27 \pm 3.77 \times 10^7$

4.1.2.1 Graphical presentation of bacterial load in gher 1 water

Figure 4. Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of water sample

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 1 water

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 1 water samples was analyzed. Numbers of enteric bacteria in water varied in different samplings and were found both in gher analysis and laboratory analysis (Table 4).

Table 4. Number of enteric bacteria in water sample of gher 1 (cfu/ml)

Types	In fresh samples	In iced samples
In EMB	24.67±26.39	60.00±23.43
In SS	53.00±8.00	75.33±41.49

*Values given are mean (±SD)

4.1.2.2 Graphical presentation of bacterial load in gher 1 sediment

Figure 5. Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of sediment sample

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 1 sediment

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 1 sediment samples was analyzed. Numbers of enteric bacteria in sediment varied in different samplings and were found both in gher analysis and laboratory analysis (Table 5).

Table 5. Number of enteric bacteria in sediment sample of gher 1 (cfu/g)

Types	In fresh samples	In iced samples
In EMB	97.33±61.74	67.33±16.50
In SS	135.33±91.53	46.00±29.51

*Values given are mean (±SD)

4.1.2.3 Graphical presentation of bacterial load in gher 1 prawn

Figure 6. Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of prawn sample

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 1 prawn

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 1 prawn samples was analyzed. Numbers of enteric bacteria in prawn varied in different samplings and were found both in gher analysis and laboratory analysis (Table 6).

Table 6. Number of enteric bacteria in prawn sample of gher 1 (cfu/g)

Types	In fresh samples	In iced samples
In EMB	259.67±195.30	35.00±9.90
In SS	108.33±88.12	44.67±28.29

*Values given are mean (±SD)

4.1.3 Total number of bacterial isolates and percentage of Gram +ve and Gram -ve bacteria

In different samplings the numbers of bacterial isolates were different and in gher 1, the percentage of Gram +ve was 27.66% and Gram -ve was 72.33% (Table 7).

Table 7. Total number of bacterial isolates in water, sediment and prawn and percentage of Gram +ve and Gram -ve bacteria

Samples	1 st sampling			2 nd sampling			3 rd sampling		
	Number of isolates	Gram +ve	Gram -ve	Number of isolates	Gram +ve	Gram -ve	Number of isolates	Gram +ve	Gram -ve
Water	4	1(25%)	3(75%)	5	2(40%)	3(60%)	4	1(25%)	3(75%)
Sediment	6	3(50%)	3(50%)	6	2(34%)	4(66%)	5	1(20%)	4(80%)
Prawn	7	1(14%)	6(86%)	7	1(14%)	6(86%)	6	2(34%)	4(66%)
Total	17	5(29%)	12(71%)	18	5(28%)	13(72%)	15	4(26%)	11(74%)

4.2 Bacteriological study of gher 2

4.2.1 Physico-chemical parameters

Water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), pH, and dissolved oxygen (mg/l) were recorded. Water temperature in gher 2 was 23.6 to 30.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The air temperature was recorded as 25.9 to 33.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The pH of water was 6.1 to 7.1. The pH of sediment was recorded 3.5 to 4.0. The salinity of water was 9 to 11 ppt. The dissolved oxygen (DO) of water was 4.65 to 5.16 mg/l (Table 8).

Table 8. Physico-chemical parameters of gher 2

Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)		pH		Salinity (ppt.)	DO (mg/l)
Water	Air	Water	Sediment		
27.30 \pm 3.40	29.80 \pm 3.72	6.63 \pm 0.50	3.77 \pm 0.25	9.33 \pm 1.15	4.92 \pm 0.26

*Values given are mean (\pm SD)

4.2.2 Quantitative analysis of bacteria in gher 2

During the period of study, bacterial loads in gher were 6.52 \times 10⁴-1.30 \times 10⁵-cfu/ml in water; 9.63 \times 10⁸-1.12 \times 10⁹ cfu/g in sediment and 2.50 \times 10⁶ -9.16 \times 10⁶ cfu/g in prawn when analysis was done by using fresh samples at gher (Table 9). By using iced samples in laboratory bacterial loads were 7.30 \times 10⁵-1.89 \times 10⁶ cfu/ml in water; 9.29 \times 10⁹-3.18 \times 10¹⁰ cfu/g in sediment and 4.25 \times 10⁷-3.08 \times 10⁸ cfu/g in prawn during the period of study (Table 10).

Table 9. Bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn of gher 2 (fresh samples)

Category	Sample	Bacterial Load			Mean (\pm SD)
		1 st Sampling	2 nd sampling	3 rd sampling	
Water	Sample 1	9.00×10^4	7.30×10^4	2.30×10^5	$9.26 \pm 3.36 \times 10^4$
	Sample 2	7.50×10^4	5.73×10^4	2.95×10^4	
	Average	8.25×10^4	6.52×10^4	1.30×10^5	
Sediment	Sample 1	1.67×10^9	7.30×10^8	4.46×10^8	$1.04 \pm 0.79 \times 10^9$
	Sample 2	2.56×10^8	1.36×10^9	1.80×10^9	
	Average	9.63×10^8	1.05×10^9	1.12×10^9	
Prawn	Sample 1	7.02×10^5	4.70×10^6	1.20×10^7	$4.76 \pm 3.81 \times 10^6$
	Sample 2	4.30×10^6	5.26×10^5	6.32×10^6	
	Average	2.50×10^6	2.61×10^6	9.16×10^6	

Table 10. Bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn of gher 2 (iced samples)

Category	Sample	Bacterial Load			Mean (\pm SD)
		1 st Sampling	2 nd sampling	3 rd sampling	
Water	Sample 1	2.80×10^5	6.46×10^5	5.72×10^5	$1.13 \pm 0.66 \times 10^6$
	Sample 2	3.50×10^6	8.14×10^5	9.51×10^5	
	Average	1.89×10^6	7.30×10^5	7.62×10^5	
Sediment	Sample 1	3.57×10^{10}	4.67×10^{10}	9.87×10^8	$2.27 \pm 1.18 \times 10^{10}$
	Sample 2	2.79×10^{10}	7.06×10^9	8.71×10^9	
	Average	3.18×10^{10}	2.69×10^{10}	9.29×10^9	
Prawn	Sample 1	5.98×10^8	1.68×10^7	8.38×10^7	$1.49 \pm 1.40 \times 10^8$
	Sample 2	1.84×10^7	6.81×10^7	1.12×10^8	
	Average	3.08×10^8	4.25×10^7	9.79×10^7	

4.2.2.1 Graphical presentation of bacterial load in gher 2 water

Figure 7. Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of water sample

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 2 water

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 2 water samples was analyzed. Numbers of enteric bacteria in water varied in different samplings and were found both in gher analysis and laboratory analysis (Table 11).

Table 11. Number of enteric bacteria in water sample of gher 2 (cfu/ml)

Types	In fresh samples	In iced samples
In EMB	105.33±104.16	59.00±35.55
In SS	135.00±71.76	96.00±53.33

*Values given are mean (±SD)

4.2.2.2 Graphical presentation of bacterial load in gher 2 sediment

Figure 8. Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of sediment sample

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 2 sediment

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 2 sediment samples was analyzed. Numbers of enteric bacteria in sediment varied in different samplings and were found both in gher analysis and laboratory analysis (Table 12).

Table 12. Number of enteric bacteria in sediment sample of gher 2 (cfu/g)

Types	In fresh samples	In iced samples
In EMB	171.67±155.11	37.00±19.52
In SS	105.67±87.76	79.67±18.77

*Values given are mean (±SD)

4.2.2.3 Graphical presentation of bacterial load in gher 2 prawn

Figure 9. Changes in bacterial load in gher analysis and laboratory analysis of prawn sample

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 2 prawn

Presence of enteric bacteria in gher 2 prawn samples was analyzed. Numbers of enteric bacteria in water varied in different samplings and were found both in gher analysis and laboratory analysis (Table 13).

Table 13. Number of enteric bacteria in prawn sample of gher 2 (cfu/g)

Types	In fresh samples	In iced samples
In EMB	191.33±153.18	60.67±38.08
In SS	145.67±199.10	45.33±30.27

*Values given are mean (±SD)

4.2.3 Total number of bacterial isolates and percentage of Gram +ve and Gram -ve bacteria

In different samplings the numbers of bacterial isolates were different and in gher 2, the percentage of Gram +ve was 16% and Gram -ve was 84% (Table 14).

Table 14. Total number of bacterial isolates in gher 2 water, sediment and prawn and percentage of Gram +ve and Gram -ve bacteria

Samples	1 st sampling			2 nd sampling			3 rd sampling		
	Number of isolates	Gram +ve	Gram -ve	Number of isolates	Gram +ve	Gram -ve	Number of isolates	Gram +ve	Gram -ve
Water	6	0(0%)	6(100%)	5	1(20%)	4(80%)	4	0(0%)	4(100%)
Sediment	7	1(14%)	6(86%)	6	1(17%)	5(83)	8	2(25%)	6(75%)
Prawn	6	2(34%)	4(66%)	6	1(17%)	5(83)	8	1(13%)	7(87%)
Total	19	3(16%)	16(84%)	17	3(17%)	14(83%)	20	3(15%)	17(85%)

4.3 Comparative study between gher 1 and gher 2

The bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn of gher 1 and gher 2 were $4.82\pm 3.33\times 10^4$, $9.37\pm 4.99\times 10^8$, $1.04\pm 1.12\times 10^7$ and $9.26\pm 3.36\times 10^4$, $1.04\pm 0.79\times 10^9$, $4.76\pm 3.81\times 10^6$, respectively in case of gher analysis (Table 15). Again in case of laboratory analysis the bacterial load of water, sediment and prawn were $5.21\pm 3.42\times 10^5$, $6.30\pm 2.79\times 10^9$, $8.27\pm 3.77\times 10^7$ and $1.13\pm 0.66\times 10^6$, $2.27\pm 1.18\times 10^{10}$, $1.49\pm 1.40\times 10^8$ in gher 1 and gher 2, respectively (Table 15).

The bacterial loads were higher in laboratory analysis than gher analysis and also the load were high in gher 2 than gher 1 both in laboratory analysis and gher analysis (Table 15).

Table 15. Comparative study of bacterial load in water, sediment and prawn, between gher 1 and gher 2

Sample		Gher 1	Gher 2
Water	Gher analysis	$4.82\pm 3.33\times 10^4$	$9.26\pm 3.36\times 10^4$
	Laboratory analysis	$5.21\pm 3.42\times 10^5$	$1.13\pm 0.66\times 10^6$
Sediment	Gher analysis	$9.37\pm 4.99\times 10^8$	$1.04\pm 0.79\times 10^9$
	Laboratory analysis	$6.30\pm 2.79\times 10^9$	$2.27\pm 1.18\times 10^{10}$
Prawn	Gher analysis	$1.04\pm 1.12\times 10^7$	$4.76\pm 3.81\times 10^6$
	Laboratory analysis	$8.27\pm 3.77\times 10^7$	$1.49\pm 1.40\times 10^8$

4.3.1 Graphical presentation for the comparison in bacterial load of prawn culture system in two gher

Figure 10. Comparative study of bacterial load between gher 1 and gher 2

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION

5.1 Water quality parameters

Temperature below 14°C or above 35°C is generally lethal, 29-31°C being optimal (Akiyama *et al.*, 1982). So, it was supposed that water temperature would never rise to 35°C but it might drop down to lower critical level (14°C). For that reason, temperature was recorded at early morning. Bottom water temperature was also recorded with surface water temperature, as it remains always lower than surface water. Jia-Mo *et al.* (1988) reported that the water temperature ranged from 28.5 to 33°C was suitable for fish culture and bacterial population. Microbes can grow at wide range of temperature. The suitable temperature for the growth of bacteria is 30 to 40°C, which is not similar to the results of the present study but the reason of higher level of load in a temperature lower than optimum range may be the poor water quality due to semi-intensive culture system in gher.

Paul (1998) recorded pH value ranging from 6.51-9.45 was suitable for prawn culture. In the present study, pH values varied from 6.60 to 7.50, which was more or less similar to the findings of Ali *et al.* (2004), Dewan *et al.* (1991), Wahab *et al.* (1995) and Kohinoor *et al.* (2000). These values were also within the suitable range for prawn culture. All of the above studies agreed with the present study pH 7.0 or nearly neutral which was suitable for bacterial growth.

Habashy and Hasan (2010) found that optimum level of both temperature and salinity for growth, reproduction and hatching success of *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* were 24-29 °C and 0-8 ppt. respectively.

The measured salinity of both ghers water ranged from 6-11 ppt. and the optimum salinity for prawn culture was about 0-8 ppt. (Boyd, 1995). The increased salinity may be caused by vaporization of water (in gher 1 mainly)

and intrusion of brackish water (in gher 2). Higher levels of salinity in prawn gher may results in mass mortality of prawn.

Dissolved oxygen plays an important role on growth and production through its direct effect on feed consumption and maturation. Low level of oxygen tension hampers metabolic performances in prawn and can reduce growth and molting and cause mortality. The concentrations of dissolve oxygen in the gher were more or less similar to the study of Hasan (1998) and Paul (1998). The mean values of DO of the present study were more or less similar to the study of the Kohinoor *et al.* (2000). DoF (2001) reported that DO from 5 to 8 mg/l were suitable for prawn culture but in the sampling gher the range of DO was slightly lower. Increased temperature may be the cause of lower DO.

5.2 Bacteria

Bacteriological analysis including aerobic plate count in gher and in laboratory e.g.; determination of bacterial load in gher water, sediment, prawn and the presence of pathogenic bacteria by using some selective media were done. The present study results of bacterial load in gher (measured as colony-forming units cfu/ml for water and cfu/g for sediment and prawn) ranged from $4.82 \pm 3.33 \times 10^4$ - $9.26 \pm 3.36 \times 10^4$ cfu/ml in water, $9.37 \pm 4.99 \times 10^8$ - $1.04 \pm 0.79 \times 10^9$ cfu/g in sediments and $4.76 \pm 3.81 \times 10^6$ - $1.04 \pm 1.12 \times 10^7$ cfu/g in prawn when analysis was done by using samples in gher and bacterial load ranged from $5.21 \pm 3.42 \times 10^5$ - $1.13 \pm 0.66 \times 10^6$ cfu/ml in water, $6.30 \pm 2.79 \times 10^9$ - $2.27 \pm 1.18 \times 10^{10}$ cfu/g in sediments and $8.27 \pm 3.77 \times 10^7$ - $1.49 \pm 1.40 \times 10^8$ cfu/g in prawn when analysis was done by using samples in laboratory. Bacterial loads of water, sediment and prawn samples of two ghers were different because the management conditions were not similar and the water sources of the farms were different. The organic matter influences the load and composition of microbial population (Rheinheimer, 1985). Sediment bacterial composition and load greatly influence by effluent characteristics. On the other hand bacterial flora in prawn is the reflection of aquatic environments (MacFarlane *et al.*, 1996). It affects the storage life and quality of fishery products. The results showed the variation of

bacterial flora among the gher. The variation also may influenced by nutritional composition between the gher.

5.2.1 Enteric bacteria

Escherichia coli was found round the year in freshwater, whereas *Salmonella* was found in summer only (Al-Harbi, 2003) and observed significant coliform bacteria, including *E. coli* in fish culture ponds at 25-29°C temperature. The recommended limits for *Salmonella* spp. by ICMSF (1986) is 0 (zero). It is clear from the Table 4, 5, 6, 11, 12 and 13 that the number of enteric bacteria of the samples that were collected from prawn gher were not in acceptable limit. Cow dung and poultry faeces might be the possible causes and might have the role to increase the bacterial loads. This finding relates to the findings of González *et al.* (1999), they mentioned that the composition and level of the microorganisms associated with the intestinal tract is related to the environment as well as to the food consumed by fish. Few studies have been conducted on the enumeration and detection of bacterial flora associated with giant freshwater cultured prawn (*M. rosenbergii*). The enumerated enteric bacteria in the present study was almost similar to those reported for farmed giant freshwater prawn cultured in earthen ponds in Saudi Arabia (Uddin and Al-Harbi, 2005), bacterial micro flora associated with farmed freshwater prawn and the aquaculture environment (Kuttanappilly *et al.*, 2004) and enteric bacteria and water quality of freshwater prawn in culture environment from Kerala, India (Yathavamoorthi *et al.*, 2010). Total bacterial count and enteric bacteria observed in the present study were also comparable to that reported for farmed freshwater prawn in India (Nayyar Ahamed and Karunasagar, 1995 and Surendran *et al.*, 1995). In the present study, enteric bacterial levels in *M. rosenbergii* were high as previously reported for tiger prawn farms in India and in Philippines (Surendran *et al.*, 1995). This microbial group is important in foods as indicator of hygienic quality of foods and also as spoilage flora, (Gennari *et al.*, 1999). If the influent water does not contain high numbers of these organisms, incidence of such high numbers of these organisms in prawn may be attributed to the

feed or animal manure commonly used to fertilize ponds. The composition of the bacterial micro flora found in *M. rosenbergii* farms is typical of freshwater environments and as generally recognized, is dominated by Gram-negative bacteria (Austin and Austin, 1983). The results found in this study are comparable and similar to the results of the studies that have been conducted in different countries by different researchers that have already been discussed. In the year 2010, a total of 2770 consignments processed shrimps and fish products of different fish processing plants were tested bacteriologically in the Fish Inspection and Quality Control (FIQC) laboratory, Khulna, under the department of fisheries and *Salmonella* were detected only in 46 consignments and no *V. cholerae* was detected (DoF). Therefore, the detection of enteric bacteria in this study may correlates with the result findings of most of researchers and also with the results of FIQC laboratory of Khulna, Bangladesh. On the other hand, the highest number of total coliform and faecal coliform were enumerated in traditional or extensive management system. Therefore, use of raw cow dung, poultry faeces and raw meats, might be the possible source of pathogenic bacteria in freshwater prawn farms. The presence of pathogenic bacteria in the gher indicated unhygienic environment and the sources of contamination of prawn gher such as bird faeces, mammals, reptiles. From the present investigated result it was found that the bacterial load and number of enteric bacteria were higher because of semi intensive systems where management system was poor.

CHAPTER 6

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study was conducted for bacteriological analysis and to determine the physico-chemical parameters of two prawn ghers from Batiaghata and Rupsha upazila under Khulna district. Duration of the study was from December, 2013 to May, 2014. The study included physico-chemical parameters like water temperature, pH, dissolve oxygen (DO) and salinity of gher water; bacteriological study included bacterial load and presence of enteric bacteria in gher water, sediment and prawn samples. All analyses were done according to standard procedure.

Mean water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), dissolve oxygen (mg/l), pH and salinity were 25.73 ± 3.30 , 27.30 ± 3.40 ; 4.90 ± 0.26 , 4.92 ± 0.26 ; 7.13 ± 0.47 , 6.63 ± 0.50 and 7.67 ± 1.53 , 9.33 ± 1.15 in gher 1 and 2, respectively.

Total viable count of bacteria in water analysis of gher 1 and 2 ranged from 2.56×10^4 to 8.65×10^4 and 6.52×10^4 to 1.30×10^5 in gher analysis; 1.54×10^5 to 8.31×10^5 and 7.30×10^5 to 1.89×10^6 in laboratory analysis, respectively. In sediment, that ranged from 6.01×10^8 to 1.51×10^9 and 9.63×10^8 to 1.12×10^9 in gher analysis; 4.55×10^9 to 9.52×10^9 and 9.29×10^9 to 3.18×10^{10} in laboratory analysis, respectively. In prawn, that ranged from 2.95×10^6 to 2.33×10^7 and 2.50×10^6 to 9.16×10^6 in gher analysis; 4.30×10^7 to 1.18×10^8 and 4.25×10^7 to 3.08×10^8 in laboratory analysis, respectively. The differences between gher and laboratory analysis were occurred due to the change of freshness and time interval. The differences between the two ghers might be the different geographical location, different management practices etc. Temperature may be the major factor in decreasing or increasing bacterial loads in the gher water, sediment and prawn samples.

The number of enteric bacteria in the present study varied from sample to sample, sampling to sampling and gher to gher. The presence of enteric bacteria

in the gher indicated unhygienic environment and available sources of contamination of gher.

On the basis of the results obtained from the present study, the following conclusions can be made:

1. Bacterial load increased significantly in gher water, sediment and prawn samples at laboratory analysis than that of gher analysis;
2. Presence of enteric bacteria in the gher water, sediment and prawn sample suggested that the gher were contaminated with bird faeces, mammals, reptiles;
3. Sources of contamination should be stopped to keep the water safe for prawn culture; and
4. A further investigation is needed to know the bacterial composition of those gher.

REFERENCES

- Akiyama D, Brook J, Haley S 1982: Idiopathic muscle necrosis in the cultured freshwater prawn, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii*. *Vet Medicine/Animal Clinic* **12** 11-99.
- Al- Harbi AH 2003: Faecal coliforms in pond water, sediments and hybrid tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus* × *Oreochromis aureus*) in Saudi Arabia. *Aquaculture Research* **34** 517-524.
- Al- Harbi AH, Uddin MN 2003: Quantitative and qualitative studies on bacterial flora of hybrid tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus* × *O. aureus*) cultured in earthen ponds in Saudi Arabia. *Aquaculture Research* **34** 43-48.
- Al- Harbi AH, Uddin MN 2005: Bacterial diversity of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) cultured in brackish water in Saudi Arabia. *Aquaculture* **250** 566- 572.
- Al- Harbi AH, Uddin MN 2006: Seasonal changes in bacterial flora of fish pond sediments in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Applied Aquaculture* **18**(2) 35-45.
- Ali ML, Rashid MM, Ahmed KR, Hasan SU, Alam MM 2004: Effect of high and low cost brood feeds on the hatching and survival rate of freshwater prawn, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* larvae. *Journal of Bangladesh Agricultural University* **2** 135-139.
- Asaduzzaman M, Wahab MA, Diana JM, Lin CK 2007: Bangladesh prawn-farming survey reports industry evaluation. *Global Aquaculture Advocate* **9** 40-43.
- Austin, Allen-Austin 1983: Distribution of mannan-degrading bacteria in aquatic environment. *Bulletin of the Japanese Society of Scientific Fisheries* **44** 1135-1139.
- Avnimelech Y, Lacher M 1979: A tentative nutrient balance for intensive fish ponds. *Bamidgeh* **31**(1) 3-8.

- Avnimelech Y, Lacher M 1980: *On the role of soil in the maintenance of fish pond's fertility*. The Hague 251-255.
- Azim ME, Wahab MA, Verdegem MCJ 2002: Status of aquaculture and fisheries in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Fisheries* **2-5** 15-23.
- Boyd CE 1995: *Bottom Soils, Sediment, and Pond Aquaculture*. Chapman and Hall, New York, pp. 348.
- Boyd CE, Bowman JR 1997: *Pond bottom soils*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, New York, 135-162.
- Boyd CE, Fast D 1992: *Water Quality in Ponds for Aquaculture*. Birmingham Publishing Co. Birmingham, Alabama, USA. 477 p.
- Burford MA, Peterson EL, Baiano JCF, Preston NP 1998: Bacteria in shrimp pond sediments: their role in mineralizing nutrients and some suggested sampling strategies. *Aquaculture Research* **29** 843-849.
- Campbell AC, Buswell JA 1983: The intestinal microflora of farmed Dover sole (*Solea solea*) at different stages of fish development. *Journal of Applied Bacteriology* **55** 215-223.
- De Man JG 1879: *Some of the genus Palaemon Fabricius with descriptions of two new forms*. Notes from the Royal Zoology Museum of the Netherlands at Leyden **1**(41) 165-184.
- Dewan S, Wahab MA, Beveridge MCM, Rahman MH, Sarker BK 1991: Food selection, electivity and dietary overlap among planktivorous Chinese and Indian major carps fry and fingerlings grown in extensively managed, rain-fed ponds in Bangladesh. *World Marine Society* **10** 571-574.
- DoF 2001: *Saronica, Matsha Saptah Sankalan 2001*. Department of Fisheries (DoF), the Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, Dhaka, 79 p.
- DoF 2008. *Matshaya Sampad Unnoyon Ovigan*. Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock. Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, pp. 79-81. (In Bangla).

- DoF 2012: “*National Fish Week 2012*”, a publication on the occasion of Fish week 2013, Department of Fisheries, Matshya Bhaban, Park Avenue, Ramna, Dhaka. pp. 144.
- DoF 2013: “*National Fish Week 2013*”, a publication on the occasion of Fish week 2013, Department of Fisheries, Matshya Bhaban, Park Avenue Ramna, Dhaka. pp. 144.
- Fierer N, Jackson RB 2006: *The diversity and biogeography of soil bacterial communities*. National Academy of Sciences of the USA **103**(3) 626-631.
- Gennari AM, Tomaselli LN, Cotrona B 1999: Bacterial flora associated with farmed freshwater prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* and the aquaculture environment. *Aquaculture Research* **35**(7) 520 – 535.
- González CJ, Santos JA, Garcia-López ML, González N, Otero A 1999: Mesophilic Aeromonads in Wild and Aquacultured Freshwater Fish. *Journal of Food Protection* **64** 687-691.
- Habashy MM, Hassan MS 2010: Effects of temperature and salinity on growth and reproduction of the freshwater prawn, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii*. *Crustacea- Decapoda in Egypt* **1** 83-90.
- Hasan MS 1998: *Bacterial populations in the gut of the Silver carp (Hypophthalmichthys molitrix)*. ASFA Part-I. **20** 270.
- Hepher B 1965: The effect of impoundment on chemical and textural changes in fishpond's bottom soils. *Bamidgeh* **17**(3) 71-81.
- Hewson I, Vargo GA, Fuhrman JA 2003: Bacterial diversity in shallow oligotrophic marine benthos and overlying waters: effects of virus infection, containment and nutrient enrichment. *Microbial Ecology* **46** 322-336.
- ICSMF 1986: *Microorganisms in Food 2; Sampling of microbiological analysis: principles and specific applications*. International Commission on Microbiological Specifications for Foods. (2nd edition). Blackwell Scientific Publications. pp. 152-163.

- Janaki Ram P, Madhavi R 1999: Shell disease in the freshwater Prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* (de Man): Aetiology, Pathogenicity and Antibiotic sensitivity. *Journal of Aquaculture in the Tropics* **14** 289-298.
- Jia-Mao P, Zhi-Guo L, Zi-Hao L, Martinez-Silva LE, Osorio-Dualiby D, Torres-Virviescas M 1988: The intensive culture of freshwater prawn, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* In: Memoirs of the second meeting national aquaculture network, Nevia. pp. 217-236.
- Kohinoor AHM, Islam ML, Wahab MA, Thilsted SH 2000: Effect of mola (*A. mola*, Ham.) on the growth and production of carps in polyculture. *Bangladesh Journal of Fisheries Research* **2** 119-126.
- Kunda M, Azim ME, Wahab MA, Dewan S, Roos N, Thilsted SH 2008: Potential of mixed culture of freshwater prawn, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* and self-recruiting small species mola, *Amblypharyngodon mola* in rotational rice-fish/prawn culture systems in Bangladesh. *Aquaculture Research* **39** 506-517.
- Kuttanappilly V, Surendran K 2004: Bacterial microflora associated with farmed freshwater prawn (*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*) (de Man) and the aquaculture environment, in Karala India. *Aquaculture Research* **35**(7) 629-635, Published Online: 29 Apr 2004, Journal Compilation © 2010 Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
- La Rosa T, Mirto S, Favaloro E, Savona B, Sara G, Danovaro R, Mazzola A 2002: Impact on the water column biogeochemistry of a Mediterranean mussel and fish farm. *Water Research* **36** 251-259.
- La Rosa T, Mirto S, Mazzola A, Maugeri TL 2004: Benthic microbial indicators of fish farm impact in a coastal area of the Tyrrhenian Sea. *Aquaculture* **230** 153-167.
- Liao M, Lu S, Xie C, Zhang M, He X 2012: A quick epifluorescence microscopy method for sediment bacteria enumeration. *Journal of Food, Agriculture and Environment* **10**(1) 946-948.

- Lightner DV 1996: A hand book of shrimp pathology and diagnostic procedures for disease of culture penaeid shrimp. *World Aquaculture Society* **21**(2) 322- 368.
- Logue JB, Robinson CT, Meier C, Van der Mee JR 2004: Relationship between Sediment Organic Matter, Bacteria Composition, and the Ecosystem Metabolism of Alpine Streams. *Limnological Oceanography* **49**(6) 2001-2010.
- MacFarlane RD, Maclaghim JJ, Bollok GI 1996: Quantitative and qualitative analysis of gut flora of sea bass from estuary and coastal marine environments. *Journal of Wildlife Diseases* **22** 344-348.
- Miyamoto G, Brock J, Nakamura R, Nakagawa L, Shimojo R, Sato V, Akita G 1983: A preliminary microbiological and water quality survey of two Hawaiian prawn (*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*) hatcheries. In: Proceedings of the First International Conference on Warm water Aquaculture, Crust.
- Moriarty DJW 1997: The role of microorganisms in aquaculture ponds. *Aquaculture* **151**(1-4) 333-349.
- Nayyar Ahmed I, Karunasagar K 1995: *Microbiology of cultured shrimps in India*. FAO Fisheries Report 514, 13-22. FAO, Rome, Italy.
- Nealson KH 1997: Review of Sediment bacteria: Who's There, What Are They Doing, and What's New? *Earth Planetary Sciences* **25** 403-434.
- Nieto TP, Toranzo AE, Barja JL 1984: Comparison between the bacterial floras associated with fingerling rainbow trout cultured in two different hatcheries in the northwest of Spain. *Aquaculture* **42** 193-206.
- Ninagawa T, Toshihiro N, Muroga K 1983: *Edwardseilla tarda* in culture environment. *Fish Pathology* **17** 243-250.
- Ogbulie JN, Cobiajuru IO 2003: Bacteriological water quality changes and substrate specificity of isolates associated with *Clarius lazera* culture system. *Journal of Aquaculture Setting* **18**(2) 105-112.

- Paul S 1998: Comparison between carp polyculture system with silver carp (*Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*) and small indigenous fish mola (*Amblypharyngodon mola*). MS dissertation, Department of Fisheries Management, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh. Pp. 85.
- Rheinheimer G 1985: Aquatic Microb. University of Kiel. West Germany. John Wiley and Sons. New York, 3 342- 346.
- Sestanovic S, Solic M, Krstulovic N, Bogner D 2005: Volume, abundance and biomass of sediment bacteria in the eastern mid Adriatic Sea. *Acta Adriatica* **46**(2) 177-191.
- Shao KK, Gao GG, Qin BB, Tang XX, Wang YY, Chi KK, Dai JJ 2011: *Comparing sediment bacterial communities in the macrophyte-dominated and algae-dominated areas of eutrophic Lake Taihu, China*. *Crossref* **57**(4) 263- 721.
- Shewan JM, Hobbs G 1967: The bacteriology of fish spoilage and preservation, in D.J.D. Hockenhull. *Industrial Microbiology* Ed. Progress, Illffe Books, London. England, **10** 205-341.
- Smith PT 1993: Prawn farming in Australia- sediment is a major issue. *Australian Fisheries* **52**(12) 29-32.
- Sugita H, Tokuyama K, Deguchi Y 1985: The intestinal microflora of carp, *Cyprinus carpio*, grass carp, *Ctenopharyngodon idella* and tilapia, *Sarotheradon niloticus*. *Bulletin of the Japanese Society of Scientific Fisheries* **51** 1325- 1329.
- Surendran PK, Thampuran N, Gopakumar K 1995: Microbial profile of cultured fishes and prawns viz their spoilage and contamination. FAO Fisheries Report No. 514 supplement, p. 1-12. FAO, Rome, Italy.
- Torsvik V, Sorheim R, Goksoyr J 1996: Total bacterial diversity in soil and sediment communities. *Journal of Industrial Microbiology and Biotechnology* **17** 170-178.
- Uddin MN, Al-Harbi AH 2005: Quantitative and Qualitative Bacterial Flora of Giant Freshwater Prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* Cultured in

- Earthen Ponds in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Aquatic Animal Health* **17** 244-250.
- Van Dual FC, Van Raaphorst W, Kop AJ 1993: Benthic bacterial production and nutrient sediment- water exchange in sandy North Sea sediments. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* **100** 85-95.
- Wahab MA, Ahmed ZF, Islam MA, Rahmatullah SM 1995: Effect of introduction of common carp, *Cyprinus carpio* (L) on the pond ecology and growth of fish in polyculture. *Aquaculture Research* **26** 619-628.
- Walling E, Vourey E, Ansquer D, Beliaeff B, Goarant C 2010: *Vibrio nigripulchritudo* monitoring and strain dynamics in shrimp pond sediments. *Journal of Applied Microbiology* **108**(6) 2003-2011.
- Yathavamoorthi RA, Surendraraj LA, Sabeena KH 2010: Enteric Bacteria and Water Quality of Freshwater Prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* in Culture Environment from Kerala, *Indian Fisheries Aquatic Sciences* **5** 282-292.
- Zeng, Y, Ma Y, Wei C, Jiao N, Tang K, Wu Z, Jian J 2010: Bacterial diversity in various coastal mariculture ponds in Southeast China and in diseased eels as revealed by culture and culture-independent molecular techniques. *Aquaculture Research* **41** 172-186.
- Zhang YJ, Dong B, Yang J, Ling, Wang Y, Zhang S 2009: Bacterial community structure of mangrove sediments in relation to environmental variables accessed by 16S rRNA gene- denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis fingerprinting. *Scientia Marina* **73**(3) 487-498.